

Efficacy of trimebutine maleate as treatment for patients with functional gastrointestinal disorders: a multicenter prospective trial

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Abstract

Trimebutine, a selective antispasmodic and gastrointestinal motility modulator, was evaluated for symptom control in functional dyspepsia and overlapping functional gastrointestinal disorders. A multicenter, prospective observational study was conducted in four centers in Sofia, Bulgaria, enrolling 161 patients aged 24–75 years diagnosed according to the Rome IV criteria. All patients received trimebutine maleate 300 mg once daily for four weeks, with symptom severity assessed on a 0–5 self-reported scale. At study completion, more than 90% of patients demonstrated symptomatic improvement across upper and lower gastrointestinal symptoms. No statistically significant difference was observed between trimebutine monotherapy and combined proton pump inhibitor therapy in alleviating upper gastrointestinal symptoms at week four. The findings suggest that trimebutine at a 300 mg daily dose is effective in reducing functional gastrointestinal symptoms over a four-week period. These results support further investigation through randomized controlled trials to confirm efficacy and optimize combination strategies.

Keywords

functional dyspepsia, gastrointestinal motility, irritable bowel syndrome, trimebutine

Introduction

Trimebutine is a widely prescribed pharmaceutical agent with primary activity in the gastrointestinal tract. Although less extensively recognized than some other therapeutic agents, its clinical relevance in the management of digestive disorders—particularly irritable bowel syndrome (IBS)—has been well established. Trimebutine functions as an antispasmodic and modulator of gastrointestinal motility, exerting its effects through selective interaction with peripheral opioid receptors involved in the regulation of intestinal motility and visceral pain. This selective mechanism allows trimebutine to modulate gastrointestinal function without inducing the central sedative or addictive effects commonly associated with other opioid receptor-active agents (Camilleri and Tack 2010; Lacy et al. 2013; Xiong et al. 2019; Francis and Zavala 2020).

Irritable bowel syndrome is a prevalent functional gastrointestinal disorder affecting the large intestine and is characterized by symptoms such as abdominal pain, bloating, and alternating bowel habits, including diarrhea and constipation (Mimidis and Tack 2008; Masuy et al. 2019). Trimebutine is commonly used in the management of IBS due to its ability to normalize bowel motility and alleviate associated symptoms. Functional gastrointestinal disorders comprise a heterogeneous group of conditions in which gastrointestinal symptoms occur in the absence of identifiable structural abnormalities. In a subset of patients, symptoms may involve both the upper and lower gastrointestinal tract, a condition described as overlap syndrome (Futagami et al. 2011; Futagami 2018).

To standardize the diagnosis of functional gastrointestinal disorders, the Rome Foundation developed the internationally accepted Rome diagnostic criteria. According to the Rome III classification, functional dyspepsia is defined by four cardinal symptoms: epigastric pain, bothersome postprandial fullness, epigastric burning, and early satiety, and is further subdivided into epigastric pain syndrome and postprandial distress syndrome. The updated Rome IV criteria refined these definitions by emphasizing the clinical relevance of bothersome symptoms and recognizing the frequent coexistence of epigastric pain syndrome and postprandial distress syndrome as an overlap entity, which is more commonly observed in hospital-based populations (Carbone and Tack 2014; Aro et al. 2015; Futagami et al. 2018).

The aim of the present study was to evaluate the efficacy of trimebutine administered as monotherapy and in combination with proton pump inhibitors in patients with functional dyspepsia. To this end, a multicenter, prospective study was conducted in which trimebutine was

administered at a dose of 300 mg once daily for four weeks to patients diagnosed with functional dyspepsia.

Materials and methods

A prospective study was carried out in four centers in Sofia, Bulgaria, from January 2022 to January 2026. Patients with functional dyspepsia as determined by the Rome IV criteria, with exacerbated disease experiencing epigastric pain and discomfort at least once weekly and symptoms of irritable bowel syndrome without diarrhea, were included. All subjects had undergone upper and lower endoscopy for exclusion of other pathology. Patients who had received proton pump inhibitor therapy for functional dyspepsia before starting the observation did not receive a proton pump inhibitor during the study. All subjects received therapy with trimebutine maleate 300 mg once daily for four weeks.

Inclusion criteria were the following: (1) ambulant male and nonpregnant female subjects; (2) age between 24 and 75 years at the time of the first week; (3) history of epigastric and/or abdominal pain or discomfort; (4) absence of macroscopic findings from the esophagus, stomach, duodenum, and colon during endoscopy performed 1 to 30 days before starting therapy; and (5) willingness to take the therapy and provide information regarding symptoms.

Exclusion criteria were the following: (1) alarm symptoms—weight loss, vomiting, hematemesis, melena, fever, jaundice, or any other sign indicating serious or virulent disease; (2) chronic serious constipation or diarrhea; (3) predominantly retrosternal burning pain; (4) serious or uncontrolled diseases; (5) peptic ulcer disease (diagnosed by endoscopy) and other significant gastrointestinal disease; (6) history of peptic, gallbladder, or other abdominal surgery; (7) pregnancy or breastfeeding; (8) detection of abnormal physical, hematological, or biochemical characteristics; (9) use of nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drugs; (10) use of platelet aggregation inhibitors; (11) alcoholism; and (12) known hypersensitivity to trimebutine. Every subject had to assess symptoms from 0 to 5, where 0 is absence and 5 is the most intense. The assessment of symptoms before therapy and during therapy was based on subject self-assessment surveys, where score “0” is absence of symptoms and score “5” is severe symptoms.

Descriptive statistics were used for demographic and medical data. Data are presented as mean and standard deviation and as numbers or percentages for continuous and categorical variables. The data were processed with PSPP.

Results

A total of 161 patients were observed during the period. All received therapy with trimebutine maleate 300 mg daily for four weeks. Some patients who had upper gastrointestinal tract symptoms received combined therapy with a proton pump inhibitor for two weeks and trimebutine maleate for four weeks. The mean age was 46.15 ± 11.92 years. The minimum age at the beginning of therapy was 24 years, and the maximum was 75 years.

A total of 61 male patients (37.9%) and 100 female patients (62.1%) were included. The distribution of the subjects by sex is shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Distribution by sex.

		Frequency	Percent
Valid	Male	61	37.9%
	Female	100	62.1%
Total		161	100.0%

A total of 125 subjects had symptoms from the upper gastrointestinal tract (GIT). A total of 36 subjects (22.4%) had only lower GIT symptoms, and 32 subjects (19.9%) had only upper GIT symptoms. A group of 93 subjects (57.7%) had overlapping symptoms. The characteristics of the group with upper GIT symptoms are presented in Table 2. Score “0” is absence of symptoms, and score “5” is severe symptoms in all presented tables. The score is based on self-assessment after the subject survey.

The characteristics of the group with lower GIT symptoms are presented in Table 3.

The crosstabs distribution by score of symptoms is presented in Table 4. Patients without upper GIT symptoms had a score greater than 2. The largest subgroup of patients had a score of 4 for lower GIT symptoms—11.8%. The distribution of upper and lower GIT symptom scores was heterogeneous.

Table 2. Characteristics of upper GIT symptom subjects.

Grade	Frequency	Percent
0/no	36	22.4%
1	13	8.1%
2	22	13.7%
3	32	19.9%
4	36	22.4%
5	22	13.7%
Total	161	100.0%

Table 3. Characteristics of lower GIT symptom subjects.

Grade	Frequency	Percent
0/no	32	19.9%
1	13	8.1%
2	23	14.3%
3	28	17.4%
4	46	28.6%
5	19	11.8%
Total	161	100.0%

The upper GIT symptom distribution by sex is presented in Table 5, and the lower GIT symptom distribution by sex is presented in Table 6.

A total of 28% of the subjects had therapy combined with a proton pump inhibitor (PPI). All subjects with PPI therapy had scores of 3 or more. A total of 49.6% of the subjects had upper GIT symptoms and received monotherapy with trimebutine. Subjects who did not receive PPI therapy had previous therapy with PPI before treatment with trimebutine. The data are presented in Table 7.

The upper GIT symptom scores at week 0 are presented in Table 8, and the dynamics during week 1, week 2, and week 4 are presented in Tables 9–11, respectively. At week 0, 77.6% of the subjects had symptoms, and at week 4, a total of 92.5% of subjects reported absence of symptoms. A total of 125 subjects had symptoms at week 0, and 113 subjects reported absence of symptoms at week 4. A total of 12 subjects reported persistence of symptoms.

Table 4. Crosstabs distribution by score of symptoms.

Lower GIT × upper GIT	Measure	Lower GIT					Total		
		0	1	2	3	4		5	
Upper GIT	0	Count	0	0	3	11	19	3	36
		Total %	0.0%	0.0%	1.9%	6.8%	11.8%	1.9%	22.5%
	1	Count	2	0	0	2	4	5	13
		Total %	1.2%	0.0%	0.0%	1.2%	2.5%	3.1%	8.1%
	2	Count	4	0	2	4	8	4	22
		Total %	2.5%	0.0%	1.2%	2.5%	5.0%	2.5%	13.7%
	3	Count	4	3	11	2	5	7	32
		Total %	2.5%	1.9%	6.8%	1.2%	3.1%	4.3%	20.0%
	4	Count	13	10	0	9	4	0	36
		Total %	8.1%	6.2%	0.0%	5.6%	2.5%	0.0%	22.5%
	5	Count	9	0	7	0	6	0	22
		Total %	5.6%	0.0%	4.3%	0.0%	3.7%	0.0%	13.7%
	Total	Count	32	13	23	28	46	19	161
		Total %	19.9%	8.1%	14.3%	17.4%	28.6%	11.8%	100%

Table 5. Upper GIT symptom distribution by sex.

Sex/upper GIT		Grade	Upper GIT					Total	
			0	1	2	3	4		5
Sex	Male	Count	10	7	10	8	23	3	61
		Total %	6.2%	4.3%	6.2%	5.0%	14.3%	1.9%	37.9%
	Female	Count	26	6	12	24	13	19	100
		Total %	16.1%	3.7%	7.5%	14.9%	8.1%	11.8%	62.1%
		Count	36	13	22	32	36	22	161
Total		Total %	22.4%	8.1%	13.7%	19.9%	22.4%	13.7%	100.0%

Table 6. Lower GIT symptom distribution by sex.

Sex/upper GIT		Grade	Lower GIT					Total	
			0	1	2	3	4		5
Sex	Male	Count	17	6	0	9	23	6	61
		Total %	10.6%	3.7%	0.0%	5.6%	14.3%	3.7%	37.9%
	Female	Count	15	7	23	19	23	13	100
		Total %	9.3%	4.3%	14.3%	11.8%	14.3%	8.1%	62.1%
		Count	32	13	23	28	46	19	161
Total		Total %	19.9%	8.1%	14.3%	17.4%	28.6%	11.8%	100.0%

Table 7. PPI therapy by upper GIT symptom score.

Upper GIT			PPI		Total
			No	Yes	
0	Count	36	0	36	
		Total %	22.4%	0.0%	22.4%
1	Count	13	0	13	
		Total %	8.1%	0.0%	8.1%
2	Count	22	0	22	
		Total %	13.7%	0.0%	13.7%
3	Count	26	6	32	
		Total %	16.1%	3.7%	19.9%
4	Count	16	20	36	
		Total %	9.9%	12.4%	22.4%
5	Count	3	19	22	
		Total %	1.9%	11.8%	13.7%
Total	Count	116	45	161	
	Total %	72.0%	28.0%	100.0%	

Table 8. Upper GIT symptom score at week 0.

Score	Frequency	Percent
0	36	22.4%
1	13	8.1%
2	22	13.7%
3	32	19.9%
4	36	22.4%
5	22	13.7%
Total	161	100.0%

At week 0, a total of 58 subjects reported scores of 4 and 5. At week 4, there were no subjects with scores of 4 and 5.

The distribution of upper GIT symptoms by severity in graphical presentation is shown in Fig. 1 for week 0, in Fig. 2 for week 1, in Fig. 3 for week 2, and in Fig. 4 for week 4 of the treatment. The most significant reduction in symptoms is shown at the end of week 4.

Table 9. Upper GIT symptom score at week 1.

Score	Frequency	Percent
0	55	34.2%
1	28	17.4%
2	28	17.4%
3	34	21.1%
4	10	6.2%
5	6	3.7%
Total	161	100.0%

Table 10. Upper GIT symptom score at week 2.

Score	Frequency	Percent
0	74	46.0%
1	68	42.2%
2	6	3.7%
3	10	6.2%
5	3	1.9%
Total	161	100.0%

Table 11. Upper GIT symptom score at week 4.

Score	Frequency	Percent
0	149	92.5%
1	6	3.7%
2	5	3.1%
3	1	0.6%
Total	161	100.0%

There is no significant difference for subjects with symptoms from the upper GIT treated with trimebutine monotherapy and trimebutine with PPI at week 4. Subjects with monotherapy with score 1 upper GIT symptoms at the end of week 4 were 3.1% versus 0.6% for combined therapy. Subjects with monotherapy with score 2 upper GIT symptoms at the end of week 4 were 1.2% versus 1.9%

Figure 1. Upper GIT symptoms by severity at week 0.

Figure 2. Upper GIT symptoms by severity at week 1.

Figure 3. Upper GIT symptoms by severity at week 2.

Figure 4. Upper GIT symptoms by severity at week 4.

for combined therapy. Subjects with monotherapy with score 3 upper GIT symptoms at the end of week 4 were 0.0% versus 0.6% for combined therapy. It must be mentioned that subjects treated with monotherapy had pre-treatment with PPI, and subjects with combined therapy had severe symptoms. Descriptive statistics for symptom scores at week 4 are presented in Table 12.

Table 12. Upper GIT symptom score at week 4 with and without PPI.

Upper GIT Week 4 × PPI	Symptoms score		PPI		Total
			No	Yes	
Upper GIT Week 4	0	Count	109	40	149
		Total %	67.7%	24.8%	92.5%
	1	Count	5	1	6
		Total %	3.1%	0.6%	3.7%
	2	Count	2	3	5
		Total %	1.2%	1.9%	3.1%
3	Count	0	1	1	
	Total %	0.0%	0.6%	0.6%	
Total	Count	116	45	161	

The lower GIT symptom scores at week 0 are presented in Table 13, and the dynamics during week 1, week 2, and week 4 are presented in Tables 14–16, respectively. At week 0, a total of 80.1% of the subjects had symptoms, and at week 4, a total of 91.3% of subjects reported absence of symptoms. A total of 129 subjects had symptoms at week 0, and 147 subjects reported absence of symptoms at week 4. A total of 14 subjects reported

Table 13. Lower GIT symptom score at week 0.

Score	Frequency	Percent
0	32	19.9%
1	13	8.1%
2	23	14.3%
3	28	17.4%
4	46	28.6%
5	19	11.8%
Total	161	100.0%

Table 14. Lower GIT symptom score at week 1.

Lower GIT Week1		
Score	Frequency	Percent
0	57	35.4%
1	26	16.1%
2	28	17.4%
3	34	21.1%
4	12	7.5%
5	4	2.5%
Total	161	100.0%

persistence of symptoms. At week 0, a total of 93 subjects reported scores of 3, 4, and 5. At week 4, there were no subjects with scores of 3, 4, or 5.

No adverse events were reported at the end of week 4.

The distribution of lower GIT symptoms by severity in graphical presentation is shown in Fig. 5 for week 0, in Fig. 6 for week 1, in Fig. 7 for week 2, and in Fig. 8 for week 4 of the treatment. The most significant reduction in symptoms is shown at the end of week 4.

Table 15. Lower GIT symptom score at week 2.

Score	Frequency	Percent
0	100	62.1%
1	42	26.1%
2	15	9.3%
3	2	1.2%
4	2	1.2%
Total	161	100.0%

Figure 7. Lower GIT symptoms by severity at week 2.

Discussion

In this prospective study involving 161 patients, a clinically meaningful benefit of trimebutine therapy was demonstrated. The primary efficacy outcome was achieved, with trimebutine showing high effectiveness in reducing both upper and lower gastrointestinal (GI) symptoms by the end of the observation period. Administration of trimebutine at a dose of 300 mg once daily for four weeks was associated with substantial improvement in patients presenting with isolated upper GI symptoms, isolated lower GI symptoms, and overlapping symptomatology. Compared with baseline values, symptomatic improvement was observed in more than 90% of participants, while only 17 patients demonstrated an insufficient response.

Overall, trimebutine was shown to be an effective therapeutic option when administered as monotherapy and in combination with proton pump inhibitors (PPIs) for the management of upper GI symptoms. However, the absence of a significant difference between monotherapy and combination therapy highlights the need for further

Table 16. Lower GIT symptom score at week 4.

Score	Frequency	Percent
0	147	91.3%
1	12	7.5%
2	2	1.2%
Total	161	100.0%

Figure 8. Lower GIT symptoms by severity at week 4.

investigation to clarify the clinical relevance and optimal role of PPIs when used concomitantly with trimebutine.

Numerous studies have previously examined the efficacy of trimebutine and related agents in functional dyspepsia and associated functional GI disorders. One of the earliest investigations by Lüttecke et al. (1980) included three controlled trials involving patients with irritable bowel syndrome presenting with dyspepsia, abdominal distension, constipation, diarrhea, abdominal pain, and flatulence. In two of these trials, administration of trimebutine 200 mg three times daily resulted in significant symptom reduction compared with placebo; however, this effect was not sustained when the dose was reduced. In a subsequent trial, trimebutine administered at 200 mg for two weeks demonstrated comparable efficacy to mebeverine (100 mg four times daily), with no serious adverse effects reported.

Zhong et al. (2007) further evaluated trimebutine in patients with functional dyspepsia and diarrhea-predominant irritable bowel syndrome, reporting statistically significant reductions in postprandial fullness, early satiety, abdominal pain, and overall symptom scores compared with placebo. These findings support the favorable efficacy and safety profile of trimebutine, characterized by high therapeutic effectiveness, low cost, and a low incidence of adverse reactions.

The results of the present study are consistent with previous findings and confirm the potential clinical value of trimebutine in patients with functional upper and lower GI symptoms, including overlap syndromes. Notably, symptom improvement was more pronounced after four weeks of therapy compared with outcomes observed during the first and second weeks of treatment. Similar efficacy has also been reported in pediatric populations and other clinical settings (Aktas et al. 1999; Kountouras et al. 2002; Karabulut et al. 2013; Hussain et al. 2018; Kountouras et al. 2019).

Conclusion

In this prospective study, an adequate number of patients were enrolled to assess the therapeutic efficacy of trimebutine. Trimebutine administered as monotherapy demonstrated significant effectiveness in the treatment of functional upper and lower gastrointestinal symptoms, with maximal clinical benefit observed following four weeks of therapy. Further large-scale, randomized controlled trials are warranted to confirm the safety and efficacy of trimebutine, both as monotherapy and in combination regimens, and to support its potential inclusion in future clinical practice guidelines.

Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

Clinical trials: EK-01-26/05.02.2026.

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The authors declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

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Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text.

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